
A quantum-chemical analysis of the relationships between electronic structure and inhibition of SARS-CoV-2 virus by a group of cyclic sulfonamide derivatives

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Abstract A Density Functional Theory study was carried out to find relationships between the electronic structure and the SARS-CoV-2 virus inhibition by a group of cyclic sulfonamide derivatives. The molecular geometries were fully optimized at the B3LYP/6-31g(d,p) level. The electronic structure was calculated at the same level of theory. From the results, the numerical values of several local atomic reactivity indices belonging to a molecular skeleton common to all molecules were calculated. These values were employed with a formal equation developed by Klopman, Paradejodi and Gómez to obtain statistically significant relationships. The equations obtained suggest the existence, in the common skeleton, of a non classical carbon hydrogen bond, an electrostatic interaction and some interactions of aromatic regions. The results are condensed into a 2D pharmacophore and some suggestions for chemical modifications that can improve the inhibitory capacity are presented.

Keywords SARS-CoV-2 virus, Covid-19, β CoV/KOR/KCDC03/2020 strain, QSAR, KPG method, Density Functional Theory, local atomic reactivity indices, cyclic sulfonamide derivatives, chemical reactivity

Introduction

During December 2019 in the city of Wuhan, capital of the Hubei province, in the People's Republic of China, several cases of a group of sick people with an unknown type of pneumonia were reported [1-3]. This fact was reported to the World Health Organization (WHO) on 31 December 2019. In the first week of January, a new coronavirus, which is now named SARS-CoV-2, was identified as the cause of the unknown disease, called today COVID-19 (corona virus disease 2019). On February 11, 2020, WHO announces the name for this new coronavirus disease: COVID-19. The WHO declared the Wuhan outbreak a Public Health Emergency of International Concern on 30 January 2020 and a pandemic on 11 March 2020. On January 21, 2020 the Washington State Department of Health announces the first confirmed case of COVID-19 in the United States (<https://www.thinkglobalhealth.org/article/updated-timeline-coronavirus>). The patient traveled from Wuhan City, China. On January 22, Chinese officials confirm that the virus may mutate. On March 6, 2020, the number of coronavirus cases hits 100,000 globally. On April 8, 2020, global coronavirus cases exceed 1.5 million. On April 22, 2020, Germany approves first trials for a coronavirus vaccine. On June 11, 2020, Biotech company Moderna to begin final stage of trial for coronavirus vaccine in July on 30,000 participants. On August 13, 2020, WHO reports that the COVID-19 pandemic is costing the the global economy over \$375 billion per month, citing International Monetary Fund research. On

August 15, 2020, Russia begins production of Sputnik V COVID-19 vaccine. On September 29, 2020, Moderna's COVID-19 vaccine shows acceptable safety. On November 9, 2020, Pfizer and BioNTech announce interim results show their vaccine candidate is more than 90 percent effective in preventing COVID-19 in participants without prior evidence of infection. On December 18, 2020, South Africa announces a new variant of SARS-CoV-2 and says the virus seems to be more transmissible and affect young people more. On December 21, 2020, the WHO says the variant of SARS-CoV-2 that was identified in the United Kingdom appears to be more infectious but likely will not affect vaccines. On January 15, 2021, the world surpasses two million COVID-19 deaths (<https://www.thinkglobalhealth.org/article/updated-timeline-coronavirus>). On April 9, 2021, Chilean studies find that China's Sinovac vaccine has 56.5 percent efficacy four weeks after the second dose, but just 3 percent efficacy after one jab. On May 10, 2021, WHO classifies the coronavirus variant spreading in India, B.1.617 or Delta variant, as a global "variant of concern" [1, 4-10]. WHO data shows that "globally, as of 5:30pm CEST, 3 August 2021, there have been 198.778.175 confirmed cases of COVID-19, including 4.235.559 deaths, reported to WHO. As of 3 August 2021, a total of 3.886.112.928 vaccine doses have been administered" (<https://covid19.who.int/>) [11-22]. In Chile, so far, six vaccines have received emergency approval: the one developed by Pfizer and BioNTech, the CoronaVac, the Ad5-nCoV by CanSino, the vaccine developed by AstraZeneca and Oxford, the Janssen vaccine and the Russian Sputnik V. SARS-CoV-2 belongs to the broad family of viruses known as coronaviruses being a positive-sense single-stranded RNA virus with a single linear RNA segment [8, 23-28]. This new virus is the seventh coronavirus to infect persons, after 229E, HKU1, MERS-CoV, NL63, OC43 and SARS-CoV.

The fight against COVID-19 is carried out today by using vaccines prepared with different methods [5, 10, 28, 29]. Recently some reports on SARS-CoV-2 inhibition by some molecules have appeared [30-34]. It is not clear if some of them will finish as oral pills to fight this disease but for the moment they can be studied with the methods of quantum mechanics to try to understand the basis of this inhibitory activity.

In this paper we present the results of a formal quantitative structure-inhibitory activity study of the inhibition of SARS-CoV-2 virus by a group of cyclic sulfonamide derivatives. As far as we know, this is the first paper using this approach.

Methods, Models and Calculations

The Method

We employed a technique to find physically-based structure-activity relationships originated on the following ideas [35]. At the beginning and starting from its statistical-mechanical definition, a model to explain the affinity constant was proposed. Next, one or more physically-based approximations were employed to transform the assumptions of the model into mathematical equations. This approach has been successfully applied to several kinds of receptors and molecules. The next theoretical stage was to add 15 new terms to the original equation. During year 2012 this method was extended to any biological activity (BA) [36-42]. The final result of this prolonged work is the following system of n linear equations (for n molecules) [43]:

$$\begin{aligned} \log(\text{BA})_i = & a + bM_{D_i} + c \log \left[\sigma_{D_i} / (\text{ABC})^{1/2} \right] + \sum_{j=1}^E \left[e_j Q_j + f_j S_j^E + s_j S_j^N \right] \\ & + \sum_{j=1}^E \sum_{m=(\text{HOMO}-2)^*}^{(\text{HOMO})^*} \left[h_j(m) F_j(m) + x_j(m) S_j^E(m) \right] + \sum_{j=1}^E \sum_{m=(\text{LUMO})^*}^{(\text{LUMO}+2)^*} \left[r_j(m) F_j(m) + t_j(m) S_j^N(m) \right] \\ & + \sum_{j=1}^E \left[g_j \mu_j + k_j \eta_j + o_j \omega_j + z_j \zeta_j + w_j Q_j^{\max} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (i=1, \dots, n) \quad (1)$$

where BA is the biological activity, M is the drug's mass, σ its symmetry number, ABC the product of the drug's moments of inertia about the three principal axes of rotation, Q_i is the net charge of atom i , S_i^E and S_i^N are, respectively, the total atomic electrophilic and nucleophilic superdelocalizabilities of Fukui et al., $F_{i,m}$ is the Fukui

index (i.e., the electron population) of atom i in occupied (empty) local MO (molecular orbital) m (m'). $S_i^E(m)$ is the electrophilic superdelocalizability of atom i in occupied local MO m , $S_i^E(m')$ is the nucleophilic superdelocalizability of atom i in empty local MO m' [44]. μ_j , η_j , ω_j , ζ_j and Q_j^{\max} are the local atomic electronic chemical potential of atom j , the local atomic hardness of atom j , the local atomic electrophilicity of atom j , the local atomic softness of atom j and the maximal amount of electronic charge that atom j may accept [36]. These local atomic reactivity indices (LARIs) are expressed in eV like the global ones and not in eV·e as are the projected local reactivity indices coming from Density Functional Theory [36].

Note that the summation on atoms runs from one to E . The value for E is defined and discussed below. Note also that the summation on the occupied molecular orbitals goes from (HOMO-2)* to (HOMO)* and that the summation on empty MOs runs from (LUMO)* to (LUMO+2)* (with an asterisk). They are called the local molecular orbitals of a given atom. Let be \tilde{A} the set of all occupied MOs of a given molecule. The set of local molecular orbitals of atom z is defined as the subset of \tilde{A} comprising all MOs having an electron population on z equal or greater than 0.1 e. Therefore we are working with only the three highest occupied local MOs and the three lowest empty local MOs for the atoms considered in E . This method is usually called the Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez approach (KPG) and has proven its utility when applied to many molecular systems and biological activities [36, 38, 45-63].

Selection of molecules and biological activities

The selected molecules are a group of cyclic sulfonamide derivatives selected from a recent study [33]. The biological activity reported was the concentration showing 50% of virus inhibition (IC_{50}) obtained from viral inhibitory assays carried out by quantifying the infection ratios using the SARS-CoV-2 β CoV/KOR/KCDC03/2020 strain and Vero cells. Their general formula and biological activity are displayed, respectively, in Fig. 1 and Table 1.

Figure 1: General formula of cyclic sulfonamide derivatives

Table 1: Cyclic sulfonamide derivatives and their SARS-CoV-2 virus inhibitory capacity

Mol.	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	X ₅	X ₆	log (IC ₅₀)
1	H	H	F	H	F	H	1.18
2	H	H	F	H	OCF ₃	H	0.95
3	H	H	F	H	H	CF ₃	0.72
4	H	H	H	H	OCF ₃	H	1.06
5	H	F	H	H	OCF ₃	H	1.00
6	H	CN	H	H	OCF ₃	H	1.16
7	H	Cl	H	H	OCF ₃	H	1.08
8	H	Cl	F	H	OCF ₃	H	0.96
9	H	H	Cl	H	OCF ₃	H	0.93
10	H	H	CN	H	OCF ₃	H	1.16
11	H	H	OCH ₃	H	OCF ₃	H	1.06

12	H	F	H	H	H	CF ₃	0.85
13	H	CN	H	H	H	CF ₃	1.03
14	H	Cl	H	H	H	CF ₃	0.61
15	H	Cl	F	H	H	CF ₃	0.40
16	H	H	Cl	H	H	CF ₃	0.60
17	H	H	CN	H	H	CF ₃	0.97
18	H	H	OCH ₃	H	H	CF ₃	0.93
19	F	Cl	F	H	Cl	H	0.34
20	F	Cl	F	H	OCF ₃	H	0.49
21	F	Cl	F	H	H	CF ₃	-0.06

Note that X₄ is hydrogen in all cases. We included this atom for a first direct search for the possible existence of C-H carbon hydrogen bonds. The distribution of the experimental data being used here is shown in figures 2 and 3. Figure 2 shows a histogram of frequencies with the percentage of observations in the upper part of each rectangle (percentages add up to more than 100% due to the use of integer numbers).

Figure 2: Histogram of the frequencies of experimental data

We can see that more than 50% of the data is between $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$ values of 0.9 and 1.2 and that values below 0.0 represent only 5% of the total data. The gaps between groups of data are originated only because no molecule presented values of SARS-CoV-2 virus inhibitory capacity within this range. Figure 3 shows the Box-Whiskers plot of $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$ values with median and quartile values.

Figure 3: Median/Quart./RangeBox-Whiskers plot of $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$ values

We can see that no outliers or extreme values exist. Therefore, we have not discarded any experimental value for our analysis.

Calculations

As usual in this Unit, the electronic structure of all molecules was calculated within the Density Functional Theory (DFT) at the B3LYP/6-31g(d,p) level with full geometry optimization. The Gaussian suite of programs was used [64]. All the necessary information to calculate the numerical values of the local atomic reactivity indices was obtained from the Gaussian results with the D-Cent-QSAR software [65]. All electron populations smaller than or equal to 0.01 e were considered as zero. Negative or greater than 2.0 electron populations coming from Mulliken Population Analysis were corrected as usual [39]. The orientational parameters of the substituents were obtained from Tables or calculated with the STERIC software [40, 66-68]. Because the solving of the system of linear equations is not possible because we have not sufficient molecules, we made use of Linear Multiple Regression Analysis (LMRA) techniques to find the best solution or solutions. For each case, a matrix containing the dependent variable (the SARS-CoV-2 virus inhibitory capacity in this case), the local atomic reactivity indices of all atoms of the common skeleton and the orientational parameters of the substituents as independent variables was built. The Statistica software was used for LMRA [69].

Because the right side of Eq. 1 needs the same number of terms for all molecules, we have introduced the common *skeleton hypothesis* coming directly from the concept of atom-atom interactions [70]. To build the common skeleton we select E atoms of any of the molecules. These E atoms must have similar counterparts in all the remaining molecules of the set but they do not need to be of the same nature (i.e., a carbon atom in one molecule could be a nitrogen atom or an oxygen atom in another). Therefore, the common skeleton of all molecules can be superimposed, implying that these structures must be oriented in the same way in all molecules when exerting their biological activities. It is hypothesized that different parts of this common skeleton account for all or almost all the atom-atom interactions leading to the expression of the biological activity. The action of the remaining atoms is to modify the electronic structure of the common skeleton (they can also bind receptors or other macromolecules) and to influence the right alignment of the drug (throughout the orientational parameters). The common skeleton used in this study is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Common skeleton numbering

Results

Regarding the interpretation of the resulting QSAR equations, a very important point to stress is the following. When a local atomic reactivity index of an inner occupied local MO (i.e., (HOMO-1)* and/or (HOMO-2)*) or of a higher vacant local MO ((LUMO+1)* and/or (LUMO+2)*) appears in any equation, this means that the remaining of the upper occupied local MOs (for example, if (HOMO-2)* appears, upper means (HOMO-1)* and (HOMO)*) or the remaining of the empty local MOs (for example, if (LUMO+1)* appears, lower means the (LUMO)*) also contribute to the interaction. Their absence in the equation only means that the variation of their numerical values does not account for the variation of the numerical value of the biological property. In this case, it is considered that the absent local MOs behave in the same way that the local MOs appearing into the equations. A second point is the appearance of outliers in some equations during the LMRA process. As it is well known, single outliers can considerably change the slope of the regression line and therefore the value of the correlation. Also, outliers artificially increase the value of a correlation coefficient and also decrease the value of a genuine correlation. Outliers were removed when detected. Two LRMA techniques were used: the Ridge regression and the forward stepwise method. The first one, forward stepwise (FS), begins with a model that contains no variables. Then starts adding or deleting the most significant variables one after the other depending on the choice of F to enter or F to remove values until the "best" regression model is obtained. Ridge regression analysis is a method of estimating the coefficients of multiple regression models in situations where independent variables are highly correlated. It is a technique to create a model when the number of predictor variables in a set exceeds the number of observations (this is the usual case in QSAR studies, especially in the KPG method), or when a data set has multicollinearity (correlations between predictor variables).

Results for the forward stepwise LMRA

During the FS LRMA procedure one data appeared as being an outlier and was removed from the set. The best equation was:

$$\log(\text{IC}_{50}) = 1.20 - 1.00 S_{37}^N (\text{LUMO}+2)^* + 0.012 S_8^N (\text{LUMO}+2)^* \quad (2)$$

with $n=20$, $R=0.95$, $R^2=0.91$, $\text{adj-}R^2=0.90$, $F(2,17)=87.458$ ($p<0.00001$) and $SD=0.10$. No outliers were present and no residuals fall outside the $\pm 2\sigma$ limits. Here, $S_{37}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ is the nucleophilic superdelocalizability of the third lowest empty local MO of atom 37 and $S_8^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ is the nucleophilic superdelocalizability of the third lowest empty local MO of atom 8. Tables 2 and 3 show the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of coefficients and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 2. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 3). Figure 5 displays the plot of observed vs. calculated values.

Table 2: Beta coefficients and t-test for significance of coefficients in Eq. 2

Variable	Beta	t(17)	p-level
$S_{37}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	-0.70	-9.53	<0.000001
$S_8^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	0.56	7.63	0.000001

Table 3: Matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables in Eq. 2

	$S_{37}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	$S_8^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$
$S_{37}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	1	
$S_8^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	0.02	1

Figure 5: Plot of predicted vs. observed $\log(IC_{50})$ values (Eq. 2). Dashed lines denote the 95% confidence interval. The associated statistical parameters of Eq. 2 indicate that this equation is statistically significant and that the variation of the numerical values of a group of only two local atomic reactivity indices of atoms constituting the common skeleton explains about 90% of the variation of $\log(IC_{50})$. Figure 5, spanning about 1.3 orders of magnitude, shows that there is a relatively good correlation of observed versus calculated values. Figures 6, 7 and 8 show, respectively, the plot of predicted values vs. residuals scores, the plot of residual vs. deleted residuals and the normal probability plot of residuals.

Figure 6: Plot of predicted values vs. residuals scores

Figure 7: Plot of residual vs. deleted residuals

Figure 8: Normal probability plot of residuals

The distribution of points in these three plots shows that the assumption of linearity is a good first approach. Therefore, equation 2 is suitable to deal with the structure-activity relationships.

Results for the Ridge LMRA

During the LRMA three data appeared as being outliers and were removed from the set. The best equation was:

$$\log(\text{IC}_{50}) = 1.16 - 0.60S_{37}^N (\text{LUMO}+2)^* - 0.01\phi_1 - 0.60F_{17}(\text{HOMO}-2)^* + 0.37Q_{26} \quad (3)$$

with $n=18$, $R=0.99$, $R^2=0.99$, $\text{adj-}R^2=0.99$, $F(4,13)=313.91$ ($p<0.00001$) and $SD=0.04$. No outliers were detected and no residuals fall outside the $\pm 2\sigma$ limits. Here, $S_{37}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ is the nucleophilic superdelocalizability of the third lowest empty local MO of atom 37, ϕ_1 is the orientational parameter of substituent X_1 , $F_{17}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$ is the Fukui index of the third highest occupied local MO of atom 17 and Q_{26} is the net charge of atom 26. Tables 4 and 5 show the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of coefficients and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 3. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 5). Figure 9 displays the plot of observed vs. calculated values.

Table 4: Beta coefficients and t-test for significance of coefficients in Eq. 3

Variable	Beta	t(13)	p-level
$S_{37}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	-0.41	-11.42	0.000000
ϕ_1	-0.44	-12.91	0.000000
$F_{17}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$	-0.28	-7.61	0.000004
Q_{26}	0.23	6.82	0.00001

Table 5: Matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables in Eq. 3

	$S_{37}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	ϕ_1	$F_{17}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$	Q_{26}
$S_{37}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$	1			
ϕ_1	0.08	1		
$F_{17}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$	0.18	0.32	1	
Q_{26}	0.30	0.02	0.04	1

Figure 9. Plot of predicted *vs.* observed $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$ values (Eq. 3). Dashed lines denote the 95% confidence interval. The associated statistical parameters of Eq. 3 indicate that this equation is statistically significant and that the variation of the numerical values of a group of four local atomic reactivity indices of atoms constituting the common skeleton and the orientational effect of one substituent explains about 99% of the variation of $\log(\text{IC}_{50})$. Figure 9, spanning about 1.4 orders of magnitude, shows that there is a good correlation of observed *versus* calculated values. Figures 10, 11 and 12 show, respectively, the plot of predicted values *vs.* residuals scores, the plot of residual *vs.* deleted residuals and the normal probability plot of residuals (Eq. 3).

Figure 10: Plot of predicted values *vs.* residuals scores

Figure 11: Plot of residual vs. deleted residuals

Figure 12: Normal probability plot of residuals

The distribution of points in these three plots shows that the assumption of linearity is a good first approach. Therefore, equation 2 is also apt to deal with the structure-activity relationships.

Local Molecular Orbitals

Tables 6 and 7 show the local MO structure of atoms 8, 17, 26 and 37 (see Fig. XX). Nomenclature: Molecule (HOMO) / (HOMO-2)* (HOMO-1)* (HOMO)* - (LUMO)* (LUMO+1)* (LUMO+2)*[71].

Table 6: Local Molecular Orbitals of atoms 8, 17 and 26.

Mol.	Atom 8	Atom 17	Atom 26
1 (121)	119π120π121π-122π123π124σ	116π117π119π-124π126π128π	118π120π121π-125π127π129π
2 (137)	135π136π137π-138π139π140π	132π133π135π-140π142π144π	134π136π137π-141π143π145π
3 (133)	131π132π133π-134π135π136π	128π130π131π-136π138π140π	129π132π133π-137π139π141π
4(133)	131π132π133π-134π135π 136π	128π129π131π-136π139π140π	130π132π133π-137π138π141π
5(137)	135σ136π137π-138π139π140π	132π133π135π-138π140π143π	134π136π137π-141π142π145π
6 (139)	136π138π139π-140π141π142π	134π135π136π-140π143π144π	137π138π139π-144π145π147π
7 (141)	139π140π141π-142π143π144π	136π137π139π-144π146π148π	138π140π141π-145π147π149π
8 (145)	143π144π145π-146π147π148π	140π141π143π-148π149π150π	142π144π145π-149π151π153π
9 (141)	139π140π141π-142π143π144π	136π137π139π-144π146π148π	138π140π141π-145π147π149π
10 (139)	136σ138π139π-140π141π142π	134π135π136π-140π141π142π	137π138π139π-143π145π146π
11 (141)	139π140π141π-142π143π144π	139π140π141π-146π148π150π	138π140π141π-145π147π149π

12 (133)	131σ132π133π-134π135π136π	128π130π131π-134π135π136π	129π132π133π-137π138π141π
13 (135)	133π134π135π-136π137π138π	130π131π133π-136π139π140π	126π134π135π-139π140π141π
14 (137)	135π136π137π-138π139π140π	132π134π135π-140π142π144π	133π136π137π-141π143π145π
15 (141)	139σ140π141π-142π143π144π	136π138π139π-144π146π148π	137π140π141π-145π147π149π
16 (137)	135σ136π137π-138π139π140π	132π134π135π-140π142π144π	133π136π137π-141π143π145π
17 (135)	133σ134π135π-136π137π138π	130π131π133π-136π137π138π	132π134π135π-139π141π142π
18 (137)	134π135π137π-138π139π140π	135π136π137π-143π144π145π	132π133π136π-140π141π142π
19 (137)	134σ136π137π-138π140π144π	132π133π134π-140π141π142π	135π136π137π-141π143π145π
20 (149)	146σ148π149π-150π152π156π	144π145π146π-152π153π154π	147π148π149π-153π155π157π
21 (145)	143σ144π145π-146π148π152π	140π142π143π-148π150π152π	141π144π145π-149π151π153π

Table 7: Local Molecular Orbitals of atom 37

Mol.	Atom 37
1 (121)	101σ106σ107σ-136σ139σ140σ
2 (137)	117 σ120σ123σ-152σ155σ156σ
3 (133)	108σ116σ117σ-148σ149σ150σ
4 (133)	112σ115σ119σ-148σ151σ152σ
5 (137)	116σ120σ123σ-152σ155σ156σ
6 (139)	117σ121σ123σ-155σ159σ160σ
7 (141)	123σ125σ126σ-157σ159σ161σ
8 (145)	124σ127σ130σ-161σ163σ165σ
9 (141)	123σ125σ126σ-157σ159σ161σ
10 (139)	117σ121σ124σ-155σ159σ160σ
11 (141)	120σ123σ125σ-153σ154σ155σ
12 (133)	108σ116σ117σ-148σ149σ150σ
13 (135)	108σ117σ118σ-151σ152σ154σ
14 (137)	111σ120σ121σ-153σ154σ155σ
15 (141)	115σ124σ125σ-157σ158σ159σ
16 (137)	111σ120σ121σ-153σ154σ155σ
17 (135)	108σ117σ118σ-151σ152σ154σ
18 (137)	119σ120σ121σ-151σ152σ154σ
19 (137)	115σ118σ119σ-148σ159σ162σ
20 (149)	128σ132σ134σ-165σ167σ170σ
21 (145)	118σ128σ129σ-161σ162σ163σ

Discussion

Discussion of the forward stepwise LMRA results

Table 2 shows that the importance of variables in Eq. 2 is $S_{37}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^* > S_8^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$. The variable-by-variable analysis shows that a high SARS-CoV-2 virus inhibitory capacity is associated with at least high (positive) numerical values for $S_{37}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ and low (positive) numerical values for $S_8^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$. Atom 37 is the first atom of the substituent bonded to atom 25 in ring D (see Fig. 4 and Table 1. It is a hydrogen atom in all cases). Table 7 shows that all local MOs have a σ nature and that $(\text{HOMO})_{37}$ and $(\text{LUMO})_{37}$ are energetically far from the corresponding molecular frontier orbitals HOMO and LUMO. Given that a high inhibitory activity is associated with large (positive) numerical values for $S_{37}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ we shall assume that this requirement also holds for $S_{37}^N(\text{LUMO}+1)^*$ and $S_{37}^N(\text{LUMO})^*$. These large values are obtained by lowering the MO energies, making them more reactive. This fact could be interpreted by thinking of the hydrogen atom as a “bridge” allowing the movement of electrons between C25 and an atom or moiety located in the macromolecule. We suggest that this could

correspond to a non-classical C25-H hydrogen bond of the C25-H...O or C25-H...N kinds [72-74]. Atom 8 is a carbon atom of ring B (see Fig. 4). Table 6 shows that the three lowest empty local MOs of this atom are almost all of π nature. A high inhibitory capacity is associated with low (positive) numerical values for $S_8^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$. The only way to obtain these low numerical values is by increasing the $(\text{LUMO}+2)_8^*$ energy, making this MO less reactive. If we apply the same argument to $(\text{LUMO}+1)_8^*$ and $(\text{LUMO})_8^*$, the atom 8 should behave as a bad electron acceptor. On the other hand, the two highest occupied local MOs have a π nature and coincide with the molecule's HOMO and (HOMO-1) in all cases. These two facts strongly suggest that atom 8 is facing an electron-deficient moiety. The interaction could correspond to a π -cation or to a π - π one [70].

Discussion of the Ridge LMRA results

Table 4 shows that the importance of variables in Eq. 3 is $\varphi_1 \sim S_{37}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^* > F_{17}(\text{HOMO}-2)^* > Q_{26}$. Table 5 shows that a correlation between the values of φ_1 and $F_{17}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$. A case of fortuitous numerical correlation is between the orientational parameter of X_1 (derived within classical mechanics) and $F_{17}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$ (derived within quantum mechanics). In this case, the variable-by-variable analysis shows that a high SARS-CoV-2 virus inhibitory capacity is associated with at least large numerical values for φ_1 , $S_{37}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ and $F_{17}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$, and with negative values for Q_{26} . φ_1 is the orientational parameter of the substituent attached to atom C-3 in ring A (H and F in Table 1). This suggests that we may change F by other electron-attracting substituents having greater numerical values of the orientational parameter such as NO_2 , CN or CO_2Me . As we saw in the previous analysis, atom 37 is the first atom of the substituent bonded to atom 25 in ring D. Given that a high inhibitory activity is associated with large (positive) numerical values for $S_{37}^N(\text{LUMO}+2)^*$ the analysis of this local atomic reactivity index is identical to the forward stepwise results: a non-classical C25-H hydrogen bond. Atom 17 is a carbon atom in ring C (see Fig. 4). Large numerical values for $F_{17}(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$ are associated with high inhibitory activity. Large numerical values are obtained by shifting toward zero the MO energy, making it more reactive. This shifting should move also toward zero the energies of $(\text{HOMO}-1)_{17}^*$ and $(\text{HOMO})_{17}^*$. This growing reactivity strongly suggests that this atom is interacting with an electron-deficient center. The interaction could be a π -cation or a π - π one [70]. Atom 26 is a carbon atom in ring D (see Fig. 4). The X_5 substituent is attached to it. Considering that a negative net charge seems to be associated with a high inhibitory activity, any substituent giving electrons to C-26 seems to be appropriate. We suggest that atom 26 is closed to a positively charged site.

The above results are integrated in the partial two-dimensional (2D) partial pharmacophore shown in Fig. 13.

Figure 13: Partial 2D pharmacophore

Conclusion

In summary, the analysis of experimental data about SARS-CoV-2 virus inhibition by a group of cyclic sulfonamide derivatives was carried out with the Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez method. The results provided information about possible sites to be modified and/or substituted to obtain chemical agents showing a stronger viral inhibitory power.

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